

Supplemental Online Content

Sommerstein R, Troillet N, Harbarth S, et al; Swissnosogroup. Timing of cefuroxime surgical antimicrobial prophylaxis and its association with surgical site infections. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2023;6(6):e2317370. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2023.17370

eFigure. Administration of Surgical Antimicrobial Prophylaxis Relative to Timing Before Incision (Histogram)

eTable 1. Baseline and Procedural Characteristics of Patients Included and Lost To Follow-up

eTable 2. Summary of the Leading Microorganism Detected in 3381 of 222 439 Cases (1.52 %) With Recorded Etiology by SAP Timing Group

eTable 3. Fully Adjusted Mixed Effects Logistic Regression Models With Surgical Site Infection as the Dependent Variable, Including the Variable *Implant* and More Categories for Age and ASA

eTable 4. Fully Adjusted Mixed Effects Logistic Regression Models With Surgical Site Infection as the Dependent Variable for the Subgroup Preparatory Room (55-30 Minutes Prior to Incision) vs Operatory Room (25-10 Minutes Prior to Incision)

This supplemental material has been provided by the authors to give readers additional information about their work.

Supplementary Material

eFigure

Administration of surgical antimicrobial prophylaxis relative to timing before incision (histogram).

eTable 1**Baseline and Procedural Characteristics of Patients Included and Lost to Follow-up**

Characteristic	Included Patients, No (%)	Lost to Follow-up Patients, No (%)	
n	222439	22208	
Age, median (IQR), y	65.69 [53.87, 74.20]	63.02 [50.54, 73.13]	<0.001
Sex = f	118392 (53.2)	12509 (56.3)	<0.001
ASA scores			<0.001
1, 2	154749 (69.6)	15074 (67.9)	
3-5	66765 (30.0)	7008 (31.6)	
NA	925 (0.4)	126 (0.6)	
Addition of Metronidazole as second SAP	19397 (8.7)	1342 (6.0)	<0.001
Intervention Type			<0.001
Cesarean Section	13426 (6.0)	1939 (8.7)	
Cholecystectomy	9831 (4.4)	1047 (4.7)	
Colon surgery	17217 (7.7)	1068 (4.8)	
Hernia repair	20652 (9.3)	1332 (6.0)	
Hysterectomy	5526 (2.5)	789 (3.6)	
Cardiac surgery	17332 (7.8)	2490 (11.2)	
Laminectomy	6586 (3.0)	370 (1.7)	
Spondylodesis	2785 (1.3)	260 (1.2)	
Gastric bypass surgery	5910 (2.7)	560 (2.5)	
Total Hip Prosthesis	71532 (32.2)	6656 (30.0)	
Total Knee Prosthesis	51642 (23.2)	5697 (25.7)	
Wound contamination class = clean-contaminated (vs. clean)	52732 (23.7)	5498 (24.8)	<0.001
Surgery exceeding standard time = yes	31807 (14.3)	3106 (14.0)	0.21
Year (median [IQR])	2015.00 [2013.00, 2018.00]	2015.00 [2012.00, 2018.00]	<0.001
Hospital size (beds)			<0.001
<200	126947 (57.1)	13325 (60.0)	
200-499	67516 (30.4)	5782 (26.0)	
500+	27976 (12.6)	3101 (14.0)	

Characteristics showed (among others), that patients lost to follow up were younger, more often female, and underwent more frequently Cesarean section.

eTable 2

Summary of the Leading Microorganism Detected in 3381 of 222 439 Cases (1.52 %) With Recorded Etiology by SAP Timing Group

Microbiologic etiology	Administration of SAP prior to incision		
	0-30 minutes Patients, No (%)	31-60 minutes Patients, No (%)	61-120 minutes Patients, No (%)
	n=1 103	n=1 652	n=626
Escherichia coli	103 (17.0)	258 (21.7)	102 (21.9)
Methicillin-susceptible Staphylococcus aureus	109 (18.0)	185 (15.6)	64 (13.7)
Coagulase-negative Staphylococcus	91 (15.0)	172 (14.5)	64 (13.7)
Enterococci (VRE or non VRE)	29 (4.8)	82 (6.9)	39 (8.4)
ESBL-producing Escherichia coli	17 (2.8)	33 (2.8)	21 (4.5)
Alpha-haemolytic Streptococcus	27 (4.5)	46 (3.9)	16 (3.4)
Enterococcus faecium (non VRE)	12 (2.0)	26 (2.2)	15 (3.2)
Enterobacter aerogenes / cloacae	22 (3.6)	38 (3.2)	15 (3.2)
Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacter aerogenes / cloacae	20 (3.3)	22 (1.9)	14 (3.0)
Enterococcus faecalis (non VRE)	21 (3.5)	41 (3.4)	13 (2.8)
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	20 (3.3)	38 (3.2)	12 (2.6)
Cutibacterium acnes	16 (2.6)	37 (3.1)	10 (2.1)
Proteus mirabilis, vulgaris	7 (1.2)	14 (1.2)	9 (1.9)
Bacteroides sp.	13 (2.1)	23 (1.9)	8 (1.7)
Candida albicans	8 (1.3)	8 (0.7)	8 (1.7)
Streptococcus agalactiae	12 (2.0)	28 (2.4)	7 (1.5)
Klebsiella pneumoniae, oxytoca, variicola	16 (2.6)	24 (2.0)	6 (1.3)
Other streptococcus	14 (2.3)	32 (2.7)	6 (1.3)
Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA)	8 (1.3)	5 (0.4)	5 (1.1)
Other Gram positive	4 (0.7)	9 (0.8)	4 (0.9)
Gemella sp.	6 (1.0)	10 (0.8)	4 (0.9)
Serratia marcescens	3 (0.5)	5 (0.4)	3 (0.6)
Clostridium species	2 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	3 (0.6)
Corynebacterium sp	2 (0.3)	5 (0.4)	2 (0.4)
ESBL-producing Klebsiella sp.	1 (0.2)	3 (0.3)	2 (0.4)
Prevotella sp.	3 (0.5)	3 (0.3)	2 (0.4)
Candida glabrata	1 (0.2)	2 (0.2)	2 (0.4)
Streptococcus pyogenes	1 (0.2)	3 (0.3)	2 (0.4)
Gut Flora	1 (0.2)	6 (0.5)	2 (0.4)
VRE	1 (0.2)	4 (0.3)	1 (0.2)
Bacillus sp.	0 (0.0)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.2)
Acinetobacter sp.	1 (0.2)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.2)
Haemophilus sp	3 (0.5)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.2)
Other Gram negatives	1 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.2)
Veillonellae	0 (0.0)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.2)

Carbapenemase-producing <i>Escherichia coli</i>	2 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
ESBL-producing <i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i> / <i>cloacae</i>	0 (0.0)	1 (0.1)	0 (0.0)
<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i>	1 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	0 (0.0)	2 (0.2)	0 (0.0)
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	0 (0.0)	1 (0.1)	0 (0.0)
<i>Peptostreptococcus</i> sp	0 (0.0)	7 (0.6)	0 (0.0)
Other <i>Candida</i> sp.	0 (0.0)	2 (0.2)	0 (0.0)
Other fungi	1 (0.2)	2 (0.2)	0 (0.0)
Non-classifiable	5 (0.8)	3 (0.3)	0 (0.0)
Skin Flora	1 (0.2)	1 (0.1)	0 (0.0)

eTable 3**Fully Adjusted Mixed Effects Logistic Regression Models With Surgical Site Infection as the Dependent Variable, Including the Variable *Implant* and More Categories for Age and ASA**

Procedure type was added as random effect. Only complete cases (221 514/222 439)

Variable	aOR	Lower CI	Upper CI	p-value
Cefuroxime timing 0-30 minutes (Ref: 61-120 minutes)	0.85	0.78	0.93	<0.001
Cefuroxime timing 31-60 minutes (Ref: 61-120 minutes)	0.91	0.84	0.98	0.01
ASA Score 2 (Ref = ASA 1)	1.43	1.27	1.61	<0.001
ASA Score 3 (Ref = ASA 1)	2.40	2.11	2.73	<0.001
ASA Score 4 (Ref = ASA 1)	2.82	2.37	3.36	<0.001
ASA Score 5 (Ref = ASA 1)	2.27	0.89	5.81	0.09
Age group 30-40 years (Ref: 18-20 years)	1.01	0.83	1.23	0.92
Age group 40-50 years (Ref: 18-20 years)	1.00	0.82	1.21	0.96
Age group 50-60 years (Ref: 18-20 years)	0.93	0.77	1.12	0.44
Age group 60-70 years (Ref: 18-20 years)	0.86	0.71	1.04	0.12
Age group 70-80 years (Ref: 18-20 years)	0.81	0.66	0.98	0.03
Age group 80-90 years (Ref: 18-20 years)	0.75	0.61	0.93	0.007
Age group >90 years (Ref: 18-20 years)	0.78	0.52	1.17	0.23
Wound contamination class: Clean-contaminated (Ref = clean)	1.40	0.89	2.19	0.14
Implant = yes (Ref= no implant)	1.13	0.91	1.39	0.27
Duration exceeding standard time (Ref = No)	1.64	1.54	1.75	<0.001
Female Sex (Ref= male)	0.79	0.74	0.84	<0.001
Hospital Size 200-499 beds (Ref= <200 beds)	1.12	1.05	1.19	0.001
Hospital Size >500 beds (Ref= <200 beds)	1.27	1.17	1.39	<0.001
Year (per year increase)	0.96	0.96	0.96	<0.001

Abbreviations

aOR	Adjusted odds ratio
ASA	American Society of Anesthesiologists
CI	Confidence interval

eTable 4**Fully Adjusted Mixed Effects Logistic Regression Models With Surgical Site Infection as the Dependent Variable for the Subgroup: Preparatory Room (55-30 Minutes Prior to Incision) vs Operatory Room (25-10 Minutes Prior to Incision)**

Procedure type was added as random effect. Only complete cases (162 129/162 796)

Variable	aOR and 95% CI	p-value
Cefuroxime timing 25-10 minutes (Ref: 55-30 minutes)	0.89 (0.82-0.97)	0.008
Female Sex (Ref=male)	0.79 (0.73-0.85)	<0.001
Age ≥40 years (Ref = <40 years)	0.92 (0.79-1.07)	0.26
ASA Score 3-5 (Ref = ASA 1 / 2)	1.61 (1.49-1.75)	<0.001
Wound contamination class: Clean-contaminated (Ref = clean)	1.38 (0.82-2.31)	0.23
Duration exceeding standard time (Ref = No)	1.71 (1.58-1.86)	<0.001
Hospital Size (Ref= <200 beds)		
200-499 beds	1.06 (0.97-1.15)	0.19
500+ beds	1.37 (1.24-1.52)	<0.001
Year (per year increase)	0.96 (0.96-0.96)	<0.001

Abbreviations

aOR	Adjusted odds ratio
ASA	American Society of Anesthesiologists
CI	Confidence interval